

THE IMPORTANCE OF ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV'S SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAN KHANATE

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Annotation: *The article details the importance of the scientific heritage of the famous scientist Asomiddin Urinbaev in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate.*

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Sources are important in the study of the political, economic and cultural life of the Kokand Khanate, which developed as a state in 1709-1876. Because the authors of the sources described the events that lived in the territory of the khanate and saw with their own eyes. While the study of the history of the Kokand khanate is recognized as one of the most pressing problems in the history of Uzbek statehood, the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev is of great importance in this regard. When world scholars recognized Asomiddin Urinbaev as a Temurid and Orientalist, it is known that he was a researcher who made a great contribution to the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate. For the first time, the scientist conducted research on the work of Muhammad Salihhoja Tashkendi "History of Tashkent" [2.1.]. In subsequent research by Asomiddin Urinbaev Abu Ubaydullo Tashkendi's "Summary of the situation" [3.1.], "History" by Muhyiddin Khokandi [4.1.], Imomali qori Kunduz (Kohanduzi) 's "Tavorihi manzuma" [5.1.], Muhammad Fozilbek's "Perfect history of Fergana" [6.1.], Mulla Niyaz Muhammad's "History of Shahrukh" [7.1.], Mirza Olim Mushrif's "Ansob as-salotin and tavorix al-havoqin" [8.1.], Avaz Muhammad Attor's "Historical Worldview" [9.1.].

According to Academician D. Yusupova, in 1964, 1971, 1987 Asomiddin Urinbaev and LM Epifanova prepared collections of Oriental manuscripts. Asomiddin Urinbaev personally participated in the creation of volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Oriental manuscripts and edited them. He reviewed the manuscript sources on the history of the Kokand Khanate included in these volumes one by one and created the descriptions of the sources in the catalogs.

It is expedient to divide the level of study of Asomiddin Urinbaev's researches on the history of Kokand khanate into three groups. The first group during the Soviet era published works are included. The second group consists of research published during independence, and the third group includes articles and works of foreign researchers covering some issues of the history of the Kokand Khanate.

The authors of the first group include A.Mukhtorov [10.1.], A.Khasanov [11.1.], F.Gofforov [12.1.], V.Ploskikh [13.1.], Sh.Vakhidov [14.1.] And others.

In his research, A. Mukhtorov used Asomiddin Urinbaev's scientific articles to cover the history of Uratapa during his time in the Kokand Khanate. The researcher also relied on Asomiddin Urinbaev, who translated the original manuscripts covering the history of the political, economic, social and cultural life of the Middle Ages.

In covering the history of Kyrgyzstan, A. Khasanov elaborated on the article by Asomiddin Urinbaev in the analysis of changes in the political and economic life of the territories of the Kokand Khanate. Based on the translation of the information given in the work "Khulosat ul-akhvol", it is described that the daily life of the cattle-breeding population, various pressures on them by the khan's officials, led to the uprising.

F. Gofforov's research covers the economic life of the khanate, and in the analysis of domestic and foreign trade relations, economic relations between Russia and Kokand, Asomiddin Urinbaev draws on the findings of local historians.

In the section of V.K. the response of the officials is highlighted [13.2.262.].

In his research included in this group, Sh.

The second group of literature includes researches published and carried out after the independence of Uzbekistan, including Sh. Researchers such as Mahmudov [19.1.], H.Burieva [20.1.], B.Babadjanov [21.1.], Z.Khatamova [22.1.] Can be listed.

Asomiddin Urinbaev is mentioned as a scholar who studied the sources on the history of the Kokand Khanate. "A. Urinbaev recognized in his time that" Khulosat ul-akhvol "is a very important source in the study of the history of the khanate," said Sh. Vahidov. [15.2.]

As K.Vakhidova's research is directly related to the sources, the comparative analysis is based on two articles by Asomiddin Urinbaev.

Z.Ilkhomov stopped Asomiddin Urinbaev's scientific researches in the process of analyzing the period of occupation of the Kokand khanate of the Russian Empire [17.2.16 p.].

When describing the history of the study of the work "History of Tashkent" U.Sultanov referred to the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev [18.2.7p.]. It is noted that the life of the author, the history of the work, its geographical names were first revealed by Asomiddin Urinbaev and O. Buriev.

Sh. Mahmudov referred to the research of Asomiddin Urinbaev in the analysis of officials in the administrative management of the Kokand Khanate, their appointment, taxation and taxation in the country [19.2.110p.].

H. Burieva draws conclusions based on the research of Asomiddin Urinbaev in the coverage of the history of Tashkent and the analysis of the origin of place names in the city. Muhammad Salihkhoja emphasized the in-depth analysis of the information on the toponymy of the city of Tashkent [p. 20.2.5; p. 10]. For example, the topography of Tashkent consisting of four districts and the geography of the surrounding lands included in the scope of these administrative units are based on the work "History of Tashkent" in the interpretation of Asomiddin Urinbaev and O. Buriev [20.3.29 p.]. The table on naming the gates of Tashkent in different sources is based on the work of H. Burieva Asomiddin Urinbova and O. Buriev "Tashkent in the classification of Muhammad Salih" [20.4.34 p.].

In B.Babadjanov's research such issues as formation of Kokand khanate, political, economic, cultural development, chronological analysis of rulers were studied, and Asomiddin Urinbaev's researches on the history of Kokand khanate were widely used [21.2.722 p.].

Z.Khatamova's scientific articles note that Asomiddin Urinbaev left a scientific legacy that provides information about the economic life of the Kokand khanate, which is important in all areas of the history of the khanate. In an in-depth study of the khanate's tax system, Asomiddin Urinbaev compares the information in this area with the information in the works of Russian historians [22.2.].

The third group of the level of study of the study consists of literature published in foreign countries, which includes J. Tulibaeva and G. Isaxan¹, S.Emishbaev, Dj. It is possible to include researches of foreign scientists such as Abdukarimov, J.Alimbaev.

J.Tulibaeva and G. Volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Oriental manuscripts prepared by Asomiddin Urinbaev and LM Epifanova were widely used in Isakhan's research. J.Tulibaeva and G. The Isakhans

¹Tulibaeva J., Isaxan G. Arabographic sources on the history of Kazakhstan: Fond instituta vostokovedenie Akademik nauk Respubliki Uzbekistan. - Astana, 2013. - 154p.

considered these catalogs in terms of covering the history of Kyrgyzstan in sources related to the history of the Kokand Khanate.

In conclusion, it should be noted that an analysis of the three groups of literature in Qori shows that the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate still refers to the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev. Therefore, this situation serves as a key factor indicating the need for ongoing research.

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